

PERFORMANCE OF KANGKONG GROWN IN ASSOCIATION WITH TIMBER SAPLINGS

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Abstract

Performance of Kangkong (*Impomoea reptans*) grown in association with different ages of timber saplings were evaluated under the Department of Agroforestry, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh during March to July, 2003. Among the different saplings-vegetable combination, production of Kangkong was the highest under Mahogoni followed by Raintree sapling; while the lowest yield was produced under Sissoo saplings as compared to control. In case of sapling ages, one year sapling with vegetable association produced the highest yield and vegetable under two year sapling produced the second highest yield while lowest yield was obtained under three years old sapling. Morphological parameters decreased consistently as the increase of sapling ages where the best result was obtained under one year Mahogoni sapling and the lowest result was produced under three year old Sissoo sapling. Therefore, considering the various competitions arise between saplings and Kangkong association, performance of Kangkong was best under Mahogoni than Raintree sapling while under Sissoo was poor.

Key words: Timber saplings, Kangkong, Sapling-vegetable association, Morphological parameters.

Introduction

Agroforestry is a production technique or method that combines agriculture and forestry on same piece of land to fully utilize the natural resources of sunlight, water and nutrition. By practicing this method, farmers can get income both from agriculture and forest products. Growing of annual crops in association with trees is becoming popular day by day for their higher productivity, multipurpose use and environmental consciousness among the people. To make the tree-vegetable agroforestry systems more productive and effective, attention should be given to identity both tree and crop species that would be compatible to each other in terms of sharing resources used for giving higher production. Mahogoni, Raintree and Sissoo are the most important timber tree species that are grown all over the country of their wider range of adaptability. In Bangladesh, Kangkong (Kolmishak in Bengali meaning) is very common and a quick growing summer vegetable has high nutritive value. Our limited cultivable land and natural resources is the main constraint for increasing vegetable production.

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On the other hand to meet up farmers timber and fuel wood demand they planted huge number of saplings of timer species in their cropland, homestead, and other fallow lands. Initially the saplings are small and it requires wider spacing and it takes many years to generate income. During this early period of tree establishment farmers can grow annual crops (vegetables) at the base and surrounding area of the saplings. Cultivation of vegetables can ensure optimizing use of our land resources and ultimately increases our total yield. Summer vegetables are short duration crops and it can grow easily at the sapling stages of trees. Considering the aforementioned facts and potentiality, a study was under taken with the broad objective to examine the effect of different saplings and it ages on the yield and yield contributing characters of Kangkong.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was conducted at the pot yard of Agroforestry Department, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh during March to June 2003. The study was carried out by factorial experiment with three replications. The pot soil was well mixed up with recommended rate of fertilizers for Kangkong. The earthen pots having 40cm diameter at the top, 24cm at the bottom and 35cm depth were used in this experiment. The following two factors were used: -

Factor-A: Three types of timber saplings.

Mahogoni (*Swetania macrophylla*)(T₁), Raintree (*Albizia saman*)(T₂), Sissoo (*Dalbergia sissoo*)(T₃) and Control= T₀ (without sapling only vegetable)

Factor-B: Three different ages of each sapling-

One year old sapling(Y₁), Two year old sapling(Y₂), Three year old sapling(Y₃). Healthy and uniform saplings of above three species were transplanted earlier in to the earthen pots and seeds of Kangkong were sowing at the surface area of the respective pot. Finally ten healthy Kangkong plants were adjusted in each pot including control. Samples were collected at 37, 54 and 71 days after sowing respectively (i.e. 17 days interval) for measuring leaf length and diameter (cm), plant height (cm), number of leaves per plant, number of tillers per plant, stem girth (cm), weight of leaves per pot(g), weight of stem per pot (g), fresh and dry yield per pot (g). The collected data were analyzed following the appropriate design of the experiment. Duncan's multiple range test (DMRT) was done to show the significance differences between the treatments means (Zaman *et al.*, 1982).

Results and Discussion

Leaf length and diameter

Among the three timber species T₁ (Mahogoni) produces the best leaf length and diameter (13.90 & 2.82 cm) and the shortest (13.61 & 2.56 cm) was recorded in the species T₃ (Sissoo) as compared to control (Table 1). Without competition control / sole crops produced the highest leaf length and diameter. Standard leaf length and diameter significantly decreased with the increase of sapling age. The highest leaf length and

diameter (15.50 & 3.09 cm) was produced under one year old sapling Y_1 and the lowest (13.75 & 2.70 cm) in three year old saplings (Table 2). According to Dhukia *et al.* (1988) yield decreased under 4 years old trees compared with those under 3 years old trees. The interaction effect between different sapling species and its age on standard leaf length was significant, the tallest (15.53 & 3.03 cm) leaf length and diameter was produced by T_1Y_1 and the lowest result (12.63 & 2.30 cm) was observed at T_3Y_3 as compared to control (Table 3). When trees and crops were grown close together, they inevitably compete each other for growth resources (i.e. water, nutrients and light) and it significantly affected crops yield and yield contributing parameters regarding their severity of competition.

Plant height

The result revealed that the highest plant height (29.83 cm) was produced under T_0 and among the different species T_1 (Mahogoni) produced the best (22.09 cm) plant height and the lowest result (20.11 cm) was observed under T_3 (Table 1). Due to the effect of sapling ages the best plant height (26.03 cm) was observed at Y_1 and the lowest (21.35 cm) was produced under Y_3 (Table 2). In case of interaction effect, except control the highest vegetable length (26.10 cm) was observed at T_1Y_1 and the worst result (17.70 cm) was produced by T_3Y_3 (Table 3). The result showed that one year old sapling produced the best vegetable length due to their less competition towards the growth resources and it gradually decreased with the increase of sapling ages.

Number of leaves/plant

Number of leaves per plant was significantly influenced by the effect of tree species, the highest (14.67) number of leaves produced by the control and among the different tree species T_1 produced the highest (11.67) number of leaves per plant while the lowest result (10.00) was produced under T_3 (Table 1). Significant variation was observed in the effects of sapling ages on number of leaves per plant. The highest and the lowest number of leaves per plant (12.75 & 10.83) was observed under Y_1 and Y_3 (Table 2). Data further indicated that the number of leaves per plant was decreased with the increase of sapling ages and it ultimately affected the total yield. It was observed that in absence of interactions, control produced the highest (14.67) number of leaves per plant and among the saplings species T_1Y_1 and T_3Y_3 produced the highest and the lowest result (Table 3).

Number of branches/plant

Initially or before 1st harvest the number of branches per plant was similar (1) in every combination. At 2nd harvest among the species the best (3.33) number of branches per plant obtained when vegetables were grown in association with T_1 and the lowest (3.00) result was produced under T_3 (Table 1). At all harvest control produced the highest number of branches per plant, among the species Mahogoni was the best than Raintree and the worst result was produced under Sissoo saplings. In case of interaction effect the highest and the lowest branches/plant at 2nd harvest was produced by T_1Y_1 and T_3Y_3 (Table 3).

Table 1. Effect of different tree species on morphological parameters and yield of Kangkong

Tree species	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf diameter (cm)	Plant height (cm)	No. of leaves /plant	No. of branches/ plant	Stem girth (cm)	leaves weight/pot (g)	Stem weight/pot (g)	Fresh yield/pot (g)			Dry yield/pot (g)		
									1 st harv.	2 nd harv.	3 rd harv.	1 st harv.	2 nd harv.	3 rd harv.
Control (T ₀)	17.00a	3.50a	29.83a	14.67a	4.00a	2.37a	166.87a	50.91a	61.60a	218.87a	523.33a	4.80a	17.00a	41.34a
Mahogoni (T ₁)	13.90b	2.82b	22.09b	11.67b	3.33b	2.00b	111.65b	37.18b	41.80b	148.37b	391.89b	3.61b	15.88a	32.97b
Raintree (T ₂)	13.81b	2.68bc	21.18c	10.78c	3.22b	1.80c	99.08c	33.81c	35.46c	133.72c	330.56c	3.00c	12.43a	27.64c
Sissoo (T ₃)	13.61b	2.56c	20.11d	10.00d	3.00b	1.76c	92.11c	32.13c	32.12d	123.74c	296.11d	2.77d	10.46a	25.23d

Table 2. Effect of different ages of saplings on morphological parameters and yield of Kangkong

Sapling ages	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf diameter (cm)	Plant height (cm)	No. of leaves/ plant	No. of branches/ plant	Stem girth (cm)	leaves weight/ pot (g)	Stem weight/ Pot (g)	Fresh yield/pot (g)			Dry yield/pot (g)		
									1 st harv.	2 nd harv.	3 rd harv.	1 st harv.	2 nd harv.	3 rd harv.
1 st Year (Y ₁)	15.50a	3.09a	26.03a	12.75a	3.67a	2.13a	138.98a	43.62a	48.42a	182.29a	438.33a	3.92a	17.86a	35.26a
2 nd Year (Y ₂)	14.42b	2.88b	22.53b	11.75b	3.33b	1.96b	110.78b	37.47b	41.98b	149.02b	380.17b	3.48b	12.11a	30.96b
3 rd Year (Y ₃)	13.75c	2.70c	21.35c	10.83c	3.17b	1.86c	102.52b	34.59c	37.83c	137.22c	337.92c	3.25c	11.86a	29.16b

Table 3. Interaction effect of different saplings and it ages on morphological parameters and yield of Kangkong

Interaction Saplings X Ages	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf diameter (cm)	Plant height (cm)	No. of leaves/ plant	No. of branches/ plant	Stem girth (cm)	Leaves weight/ pot (g)	Stem weight/ pot (g)	Fresh yield/pot (g)			Dry yield/pot (g)		
									1 st harv.	2 nd harv.	3 rd harv.	1 st harv.	2 nd harv.	3 rd harv.
T ₀ Y ₁	17.00a	3.50a	29.83a	14.67a	4.00a	2.37a	166.87a	50.80a	61.60a	218.87a	523.33a	4.80a	17.0ab	41.34a
T ₀ Y ₂	17.00a	3.50a	29.83a	14.67a	4.00a	2.37a	166.87a	50.80a	61.60a	218.87a	523.33a	4.80a	17.0ab	41.34a
T ₀ Y ₃	17.00a	3.50a	29.83a	14.67a	4.00a	2.37a	166.87a	50.80a	61.60a	218.87a	523.33a	4.80a	17.0ab	41.34a
T ₁ Y ₁	15.53b	3.03b	26.10b	13.00b	3.67ab	2.20b	142.56b	44.02b	51.60b	183.37b	450.00b	4.34b	14.8ab	36.23b
T ₁ Y ₂	13.50cd	2.83bc	21.07d	11.67cd	3.33abc	1.97c	103.2de	36.54cd	41.07c	140.37b	392.33c	3.51c	11.4b	32.45c
T ₁ Y ₃	12.67d	2.60cd	19.10ef	10.33ef	3.00bc	1.83cd	89.27ef	30.97de	32.73ef	121.4ef	333.30d	2.9de	11.1b	30.24c
T ₂ Y ₁	15.00b	2.97b	24.63bc	12.00bc	3.67ab	1.97c	128.2bc	41.35bc	42.57c	170.3bc	396.67c	3.42c	13.17b	32.20c
T ₂ Y ₂	13.73c	2.67cd	20.13de	10.67def	3.00bc	1.77de	89.77ef	31.57de	33.83e	122.1ef	320.0de	2.87e	10.27b	25.73d
T ₂ Y ₃	12.70d	2.40de	18.77ef	9.67fg	3.00bc	1.67ef	79.32f	28.49e	29.97f	108.83f	275.00e	2.73f	10.2b	24.95d
T ₃ Y ₁	14.67b	2.87bc	23.53c	11.33cde	3.33abc	1.97c	118.4cd	37.67c	37.90d	156.7cd	383.33c	3.10d	12.47b	31.26c
T ₃ Y ₂	13.53cd	2.50de	19.10ef	10.00f	3.00bc	1.73de	83.37f	30.62e	31.43ef	114.73f	285.0de	2.75f	9.77b	24.33d
T ₃ Y ₃	12.63d	2.30e	17.70f	8.67g	2.67c	1.57f	74.61f	28.09e	27.03g	99.80f	220.00f	2.46g	9.15b	20.10e

In a column, figures with the same letters do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letters differ significantly (as per DMRT).

Stem girth

Among the tree species T_1 produced the best (2.00 cm) stem girth and T_3 produced (1.76 cm) the lowest stem girth (Table 1). It was evident that in absence of control Mahogoni produced the best stem girth and it was increasing the total stem weight as well as total yield of vegetables due to less competition. The result showed that stem girth decreased with the increase of sapling ages and in regard to interaction effect one year Mahogoni produced the highest result while three year Sissoo obtained the lowest result.

Weight of leaves/pot

Effect of tree species on total weight of leaves (at 2nd harvest) of the vegetables was significantly influenced and among the timber species T_1 (Mahogoni) produced the highest weight of leaves (111.65 g) while the lowest (92.11 g) result was obtained under T_3 (Table 1). Data further indicated that vegetables weight of leaves was decreased with the increase of sapling ages and it ultimately affected the total yield. The interaction effect of sapling species and its different ages on weight of leaves was varied significantly and the highest weight of leaves (142.56 g) was produced by T_1Y_1 while the lowest (74.61 g) result was produced by T_3Y_3 (Table 3). Similar type of result was found in case of **weight of stem/pot** parameters.

Fresh yield

At first harvest, control produced the highest yield (61.60 g) due to lack of competition and among the tree species T_1 obtained better (41.80 g) yield. Fresh yield was the lowest (32.12 g) under T_3 species and it indicated that Sissoo-vegetable combination was the worst in respect of yield. At 2nd harvest the highest and the lowest fresh yield (148.37 g) and (123.74 g) was produced under T_1 and T_3 respectively. Similarly at 3rd harvest, the highest and lowest yield (391.89 g) and (296.11 g) was produced by T_1 and T_3 respectively (Table 1). Of all the harvest the result revealed that among the three timer species Mahogoni-vegetable association was the highest than Raintree-vegetable association while Sissoo-vegetable was the worst in respect of total yield, similar type, of result was found by Alam *et al.* (2001) in Tree-rice based agroforestry system.

Total yield of vegetable was affected significantly by the sapling ages at 1st, 2nd and 3rd harvest the highest yield was obtained under one year old species and the lowest yield was produced under three year old species. Fresh yield of vegetables was significantly affected by the interaction effects of tree species and its different ages. Except control, the result found that at first harvests the highest and the lowest yield (51.60 g) and (27.03 g) was obtained from T_1Y_1 and T_3Y_3 respectively. At 2nd harvest the highest and lowest yield (183.37 g) and (99.80 g). At 3rd harvest, it was (450 g) and (220 g) obtained from T_1Y_1 and T_3Y_3 respectively (Table 3). In regard to **dry yield** similar type of result was observed.

Kangkong was grown in close association with timber saplings, thus competition arises between them and it ultimately affected vegetable yield and yield contributing parameters. Interactions between tree and crops for below ground resources are often as important as those for light and above ground space (Anderson and Sinclair, 1993). At early establishments of tree species may not created enough shade effect to the associated crops due to their canopy structure. In tree-vegetable agroforestry systems root development of vegetables was affected by the tree root systems and mainly it depends upon the nature and ages of associated tree species. Researchers found that a better root development was correlated with a higher yielding crop and a basic law of agriculture was formulated that any restriction to root growth by adverse soil conditions would directly lead to a reduced yield (Van Noordwijk and De Willigen, 1987). Among the three timber species of similar ages Mahogoni root system was best than Raintree sapling for the growth and development of associated vegetable root systems while Sissoo was the worst. Therefore, yield and morphological parameters of Kangkong grown under different ages of Sissoo saplings was reduced drastically than Raintree saplings and Mahogoni-Kangkong association performed best result compared to that of control yield.

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